

Breaking of rice grain dormancy with thio-urea

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Photoperiod-sensitive varieties harvested during the wet season generally have a long dormancy period (60-90 d). Heat treatment is commonly used to break dormancy, but plant breeders need a faster method so that they can establish these varieties for a crossing program. We conducted research on methods to reduce the time for breaking seed dormancy.

We studied 14 lowland and deepwater varieties of varying dormancy and the nondormant check *Khitish* (see table). Seeds were collected from panicles within 30 d after harvest. They were soaked in 0.3% thio-urea for 4, 6, 8, 12, 16, 20, or 24 h. The untreated control was soaked 24 h in distilled water. After soaking, the seeds were thoroughly rinsed with distilled water and stored in petri dishes at 30 °C. Germination was considered positive if a healthy seedling was produced by 10 d after initiation of treatment.

Thio-urea had no adverse effect on germination of *Khitish*, even after the 24-h treatment. In the other varieties, we stopped counting for germination after it passed 95%; longer soaking periods had no ill effects.

In general, the lowland and deepwater varieties studied exhibited a wide range of dormancy. All lowland and most

Germination of rice with and without thio-urea treatment at 10 d after initiation of treatments.

Variety	Survival under submergence ^a	Germination (%)							
		Untreated	At thio-urea treatment (0.3%) duration of						
			4 h	6 h	8 h	12 h	16 h	20 h	24 h
<i>Lowland variety</i>									
Mahsuri	45	85	95	98	-	-	-	-	-
IR42	25	65	86	86	98	-	-	-	-
Swarnadhan	35	46	56	69	96	-	-	-	-
Jogen	45	0	96	-	-	-	-	-	-
BR850-22-1-4	40	45	78	89	96	-	-	-	-
Biraj	35	0	30	53	58	96	-	-	-
Suresh	60	0	48	59	68	92	100	-	-
<i>Deepwater variety</i>									
Amulya	76	0	50	58	82	97	-	-	-
SF432	70	19	91	98	-	-	-	-	-
Nalini	72	0	28	36	44	93	-	-	-
Sabita	75	0	20	34	36	85	94	-	-
Matangini	70	0	16	29	43	96	-	-	-
Dinesh	77	0	0	0	0	12	53	91	-
FR13A	80	0	0	0	0	19	40	58	78
<i>Nondormant check</i>									
<i>Khitish</i>	15	97	98	100	100	100	100	100	100

^aData taken after 12 d complete submergence at 60 d after sowing.

deepwater varieties broke dormancy with thio-urea treatment of 12 h or less (see table). Thio-urea treatment increased the germination of all the varieties tested.

Dormancy of FR13A and Dinesh was particularly difficult to break and required 20-24 h treatment to produce substantial germinability. This trait is probably related to the excellent submergence tolerance of these varieties. Seed dormancy is an advantage for them as water does not recede completely during their harvest.

The correlation between submergence (see table) and percent germination in untreated control was highly significant and negative ($r = -0.78^{**}$). The dormant varieties had higher survival under submergence. There was a significant positive relationship between survival and thio-urea treatment duration needed to obtain at least 90% germination ($r = 0.70^{**}$). We conclude that thio-urea treatment of 24 h or less can be used safely and effectively to break dormancy of rice. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Superior coleoptile elongation of rice varieties suitable for anaerobic seeding

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Poor seedling establishment is a serious constraint for wet seeded rice. Although

pregerminated seeds are sown on the surface of puddled soil, some are accidentally covered with mud. These seeds are forced to grow with a limited supply of oxygen and may fail to establish.

Tolerant varieties for seedling establishment under anaerobic conditions

were recently identified and recommended for direct seeding. This study aimed to characterize the postgermination growth habits of the tolerant varieties. Because ethylene stimulates coleoptile elongation, its endogenous production was also studied.

We tested tolerant varieties CO 25 (International Rice Germplasm Center accession no. 3697 from India), ASD1 (6267, India), JC178 (9080, India), and